

Information Theory Analysis of Human Tracking
Performance Using a Smart Stick Controller

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This paper provides an analysis of human subjects performing a tracking task while using a smart stick controller. The smart stick controller is an aircraft stick developed by the Armstrong Aerospace Medical Research Laboratory (AAMRL) at Wright-Patterson AFB, OH to improve pilot tracking performance. It operates in active and passive modes. A compensatory tracking task is developed and information theory is used to determine human operator performance. Results indicate that there is an increase in the capacity of the operator between stick modes. By viewing capacity or equivocation alone, it is not possible to ascertain any significant change in performance. However, by observing input entropy, transinformation rate, human transfer function, noise remnant, and equivocation, it is evident that a change in performance does occur from the passive to the active mode.

INTRODUCTION

Historical Perspectives. In 1983, the Armstrong Aerospace Medical Research Laboratory (AAMRL) was conducting experiments on the centrifuge to evaluate pilot tracking performance using various stick controllers. An unexpected outcome of the experiment showed that when a G-force was exerted in the direction opposed to the original stick motion, tracking performance was substantially improved. The improvement was attributed to the fact that the opposing G-force was providing a natural damping force which reduced the amount of "overshoot" introduced by the pilot while performing the tracking tasks. This led to the development of the "smart" stick controller. (8:2-3)

The "smart" stick controller is an aircraft stick controller that can operate either in a passive or active mode. It is essentially an electro-mechanical device whose internal parameters can be controlled via a computer. In the passive mode the smart stick performs like a typical displacement stick, with all forces on the stick being provided by the pilot. In the active mode, however, the stick exerts a force in the direction opposite to the desired motion. An alternate view is that the smart stick develops a force (via an algorithm) to adjust the amount of force the pilot exerts on the stick. Reference 7 contains information on design and operation of the smart stick controller. The intent was to emulate the conditions that occurred in the centrifuge. (7:810-811)

Results of experimentation with the smart stick controller have demonstrated that tracking performance improves significantly. There are two theories which attempt to explain this improvement. The first has to do with human physiology. In the active mode, the smart stick changes the muscle activity required to perform the tracking tasks, smoothing the pilot's performance and resulting in less error. The second theory is that the smart stick actually provides the pilot more information in the form of the opposing force; and since the pilot has more information available, he is able to make a more accurate response.

Purpose. The purpose of this project was to develop information theory needed to support smart stick experimentation developed by the AAMRL, and to use the information theory and the experimental apparatus to obtain information theory parameters (input entropy, response equivocation, and capacity) of various subjects performing a compensatory tracking task. The tracking tasks were performed using the smart stick controller in both the passive and active modes of operation.

Approach. A two-fold approach was used in this research. First, information theory

and appropriate assumptions were used to develop an information theory model of the human operator. Secondly, the smart stick controller was used to train and test the subjects who performed the tracking tasks.

Before testing the subjects, it was necessary to provide a training period. This was necessary because the overall goal was to measure the response of the human motor system during the tracking task. The training ensured the tracking task was a "highly learned" skill, ensuring a certain amount of predictability in the task. Each subject was tested in passive and active stick operation modes. The information theory parameters were determined for each mode of operation.

THEORY

Model of the Compensatory Tracking Task. In this study we are essentially analyzing the performance of the human operator performing a tracking task under two conditions: passive stick operation and active stick operation. A simplified block diagram for a compensatory manual control system is shown in Figure 1.

In a compensatory tracking task, the overall objective is to have the human operator output follow the system input with little error. The system input is called the forcing function, a random function representing the movement of the target being tracked. This input is essentially the ideal (perfect) human operator response. It is significant to note that in a compensatory tracking task the human operator does not see the "movement" of the forcing function, but rather the difference between his response and the forcing function.

The error signal in Figure 1 is the difference between the forcing function (target position) and the system output (position as a result of the human operator's response). It is this signal that appears on the display to the human operator. This error then is the input signal (stimulus) provided to the human operator.

The human operator block in Figure 1 can be represented by using two elements: a linear element (human operator describing function) and a non-linear element (human operator remnant). See Figure 2 below. (4:102-103)

By restricting the input (forcing function) to a specific class of functions (random sinusoids), it is possible to exactly represent the human operator response by using a non-linear and linear element as shown in Figure 2. (5:7-9) The linear element (human operator describing function) represents the linear portion of

the human operator response to a specific input. The non-linear component (remnant or noise) represents the difference between the actual output (human operator response) and the linear response. As explained by McRuer (5:6-8), remnant actually results from many different sources. In order to adequately model the remnant, the following assumptions were needed:

1. Remnant from each source is a white gaussian noise process
2. Each noise process is independent of the other noise processes
3. Each noise process is independent of the forcing function
4. Each noise process is independent of all other system parameters

Using these assumptions, it is possible to incorporate all individual remnant noise processes into a single "lumped" additive white gaussian noise process. (4:102)

The control element block in Figure 1 is the entity the human operator's response is acting upon. In this scenario the human operator's response is the movement of a stick controller to a specific position. This controller would then typically act on an aircraft. So, the control element in this case would represent the dynamics of the aircraft's response to the stick movement. For this experiment we will assume the aircraft's response is instantaneous (a unity gain in the frequency domain), essentially removing this block from the diagram in Figure 1.

Incorporating all of the elements discussed above into Figure 1 results in the block diagram shown in Figure 3 where

- $r(t)$ = Forcing function
- $e(t)$ = Display error
- $n(t)$ = Noise or human operator remnant
- $y_H(t)$ = Human operator describing function
- $u(t)$ = Human operator response (stick position)

Analysis of the Compensatory Control System. The analysis is essentially a combination of techniques used by Sheridan and Ferrell (9:207-223) and Levison (4:102-104).

The forcing function used in this project consists of a sum of sinusoids whose frequencies are not harmonically related (all frequencies are relatively prime). The power spectral densities (PSD) of $r(t)$, $e(t)$, and $u(t)$ can be determined by obtaining the Fourier Transform of their respective autocorrelations. These PSDs consist of spectral lines.

The power spectral density of the forcing function, $r(t)$ is

$$\Phi_{rr}(w) = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2T} \int_{-T}^T R(w) \cdot R(-w) dw \quad (1)$$

However, if we now restrict this integral to a very small frequency band, dw , (an infinitesimally small bandwidth about each spectral line), then this expression becomes

$$\Phi_{rr}(w) = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2T} [R(w) \cdot R(-w)] \quad (2)$$

It is significant to note that to be completely accurate, the above expression should be written as

$$\Phi_{rr}(nw_0) = \sum_n \lim_{T_n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2T_n} [R(nw_0) \cdot R(-nw_0)] \quad (3)$$

We will use the notation in Equation 2.

Similarly, the PSD of the error signal, $e(t)$, is

$$\Phi_{ee}(w) = \left| \frac{1}{1 + Y_H(w)} \right|^2 \Phi_{rr}(w) + \left| \frac{Y_H(w)}{1 + Y_H(w)} \right|^2 \Phi_{nn}(w) \quad (4)$$

Using the same technique the PSD of the human operator response, $u(t)$, is

$$\Phi_{uu}(w) = \left| \frac{Y_H(w)}{1 + Y_H(w)} \right|^2 \Phi_{rr}(w) + \left| \frac{Y_H(w)}{1 + Y_H(w)} \right|^2 \Phi_{nn}(w) \quad (5)$$

Notice these last two equations contain two terms -- one term represents the portion of the PSD correlated with the forcing function, and the other term represents the portion of the PSD not correlated with the forcing function. The latter portion represents the amount of remnant or noise power contained in the PSD.

Using Equation (5), it is now possible to write the PSD of the noise (remnant), $n(t)$ as

$$\Phi_{nn}(w) = \frac{\text{Noise in Output PSD}}{\text{Signal in Output PSD}} \cdot \Phi_{rr}(w) \quad (6)$$

The only component that remains to be defined is $Y_H(w)$, the human operator describing function. This has previously been defined as the linear portion of the human operator response. Therefore, $Y_H(w)$ can be expressed as

$$Y_H(w) = \frac{\text{Signal Portion of the Human Response}}{\text{Signal Portion of the Display Error}} \quad (7)$$

Information Theory. The human operator can be viewed from the perspective of an information channel. This analogy is appropriate since the human operator is continuously receiving information (in the form of stimuli), processing the information, and responding. Figure 4 shows the most common representation of an information channel.

The basic operation of the channel is straightforward. Information received at the input is transferred to the output. If the information is not transmitted exactly, then only two things could have occurred: some of the information could have been lost and/or noise could have been introduced during the transfer process.

Information theory measurements have their basis in entropy calculations. In information theory, entropy is defined as the amount of information contained in a signal. These signals, however, are actually random waveforms. As a consequence, the entropy can be viewed as the predictability or uncertainty of the waveform. If an output is deterministic, it is totally predictable and therefore contains no useful information. However, the entropy is related to the probability density function of the random waveform.

Equivocation and noise (often called prevarication) are conditional entropies. Equivocation, represents the entropy in the input from the perspective of the receiver (channel output). It is the uncertainty concerning what was actually transmitted given that a specific response was received. For this reason equivocation is sometimes referred to as the amount of information that is lost between the input and output. (1:58)

In similar fashion, noise represents the entropy in the output from the perspective of the transmitter (channel input). It is the uncertainty of what was actually received given that a specific stimulus was transmitted. (1:58)

The transinformation, often called mutual information, represents the entropy (uncertainty) difference between the channel input and the channel output. Therefore, it is also referred to as the information gain.

The analysis is greatly simplified primarily by the assumption that the remnant process, $n(t)$, is an additive white gaussian noise (AWGN) process. Not only is $n(t)$ an AWGN process, but so is the display error, $e(t)$, and the operator response, $u(t)$.

The entropy of the input to the human operator is actually the entropy of the output of the display, $e(t)$. This particular entropy, however, can also be viewed as the transinformation of the display and is determined to be

$$\frac{1}{2 \cdot n} \sum \text{Log}_2 \left[1 + \frac{\Phi_{rr}(w)}{|Y_H(w)|^2 \Phi_{nn}(w)} \right] \quad (8)$$

Also, the transinformation then becomes

$$\text{Transinformation} = \frac{1}{2 \cdot \pi} \cdot \sum \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Log}_2 \left[1 + \frac{\Phi_{rr}(w)}{[|1+Y_H(w)|^2 + |Y_H(w)|^2] \Phi_{nn}(w)} \right]$$

When the transinformation is integrated over the complete range of frequencies, it is called the capacity of the human operator. In this project there was a discrete set of frequencies used; hence, a summation is used instead of an integration.

Recalling that for this project the input entropy to the human operator is actually the transinformation of the display, the equivocation then becomes the difference between the transinformation of the display and the transinformation (or capacity) of the human operator.

METHOD OF TESTING

Experiments were conducted to determine the capacity of the human operator using the stick in both the passive and active mode. Six subjects were provided with a single axis lateral (side to side) compensating tracking task. The input forcing function minus the plant output was displayed on a video monitor. The plant was unity gain, so the plant output was the subject's stick output.

Control. The control stick was the primary device through which the subject interfaced with the information displayed on the video monitor. The stick was used in both the passive and the active mode. In the passive mode the stick behaved as any normal stick controller where the force was provided entirely by the operator. In this mode, the stick moves with negligible force and is called a displacement stick. In the active mode, the stick produced resistive forces on the subject's hand which were a function of the operator output. In the active mode, the stick requires substantially more force and is referred to as a force stick. The stick was allowed to move freely only in the horizontal axis for all data runs.

A transducer provided electrical outputs proportional to the horizontal displacements as measured by the rotational potentiometer located in the base of the stick. The outputs were sampled and recorded on magnetic tape and were the basis for the calculations.

Forcing Functions. Three forcing functions were used during this experiment. To insure stationarity in the experiment, the class

of forcing functions used was restricted to functions which exhibited stationary characteristics (5:12). Moreover, the forcing functions had to appear random to the subjects, otherwise the subjects could detect and learn to anticipate the deterministic nature of the forcing function.

Both stationarity and randomness requirements were satisfied by using forcing functions consisting of sums of sinusoids. It was determined that a forcing function of at least five sinusoids was sufficient to cause the target's motion to appear random to the subjects. (9:62).

In this experiment each forcing function was a sum of fifteen sinusoids, each with a random initial phase which provided for random-appearing signals. Forcing Function #1 (FF1) was generated by processing this sum of sinusoids through a second-order Butterworth filter with a cutoff frequency of 1 Hz. Forcing Function #2 (FF2) was generated by processing the same sinusoids through a second-order Butterworth filter with a cutoff frequency of 2 Hz. The third forcing function (FF3) was generated by processing the sum of sinusoids through a Gaussian filter with a 1 Hz cutoff frequency.

The initial phase shifts associated with each component were randomly selected from a uniform distribution between 0 and 2π to insure the subjects could not predict the tracking tasks. The randomness of the phases associated with each frequency also prevented large positive or negative swings. As previously stated, the individual frequencies of the forcing functions were made up of relatively prime numbers insuring that there would not be any periodicity the subjects could recognize and learn to anticipate. Table 1 shows the approximate frequencies in radians per second, the number of harmonics, and amplitudes for each forcing function.

RESULTS

As a measure of comparison, the individual entropy, capacity, and equivocation values for forcing functions 1, 2, and 3 (in both the passive and active modes) are tabulated in Tables 2, 3, and 4, respectively.

No attempt is made to draw comparisons of performance between subjects. This is primarily a result of the fact that each individual subject develops his or her own internal strategy for performing the tracking task function. For example, in discussions with subjects after the testing was completed, one subject stated he was trying to track as much movement on the display as possible. Another subject,

however, stated that he was not able to track all movements on the display, so he resorted to a strategy of ignoring the faster (higher frequency) display movements and concentrated on tracking the trends (lower frequency components) of the display. The two strategies are obviously different, but also extremely difficult to compare and contrast.

CONCLUSIONS

The overall objective of this paper was to analyze the changes in information theory parameters (entropy, capacity, and equivocation) as the subjects track a target under passive and active stick operation.

As can be seen by viewing Tables 2, 3, and 4, no conclusions can immediately be drawn from observing only the equivocation results. In some cases equivocation increases and in other cases it decreases, with no apparent pattern or trend. However, in nearly every subject there appeared to be a measurable increase in capacity; particularly when tracking forcing functions #2 and #3.

From the data obtained (available in References 2 and 6, but not displayed here for reasons of brevity), it is possible to confidently state that changes in performance definitely occur when operating the stick in the active mode. This change in performance, however, may manifest itself in a different manner for each subject. For example, Subject #5's data under forcing function #2 shows a slight increase in the gain of the human operator describing function and a significant decrease in the human operator induced remnant (noise). There is also a corresponding increase in transinformation (more information being transmitted), a decrease in equivocation (less information being lost), and virtually no change in the display error entropy. However, Subject #6's data under forcing function #2 shows a significant decrease in gain for the human operator describing function, but only a slight decrease in human operator remnant. There is a corresponding increase in transinformation (only at lower frequencies), but significant increases in display error entropy (amount of information available to the subject) and equivocation. Although the changes in performance are not the same, there is no doubt that a change in performance has occurred.

These changes in performance cannot be absolutely attributed to a corresponding change in any specific parameter. By again observing the equations in the Theory section of this paper, it is easy to see that the relationships between the input and output power spectral densities, $Y_n(\omega)$, and $\Phi_{nn}(\omega)$ are all intertwined. Also, these

power spectral densities were used to determine the entropy, transinformation, and equivocation results. There does appear to be a strong relationship between $\Phi_{nn}(\omega)$, the entropy, the capacity, and the equivocation. In those cases where $\Phi_{nn}(\omega)$ changed significantly, as with the situation discussed above with Subject #5, there appears to be a corresponding significant change in capacity and display error entropy.

In conclusion, characterizing a subject's performance merely by determining the response equivocation does not seem appropriate. However, by viewing the subject's performance in terms of the five parameters used throughout this study, it may indeed be possible to quantify the change in performance. Characterizing that change in performance, however, is a much more difficult task.

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Figure 1 - Compensatory Manual Control System (Adapted From 3:58)

Figure 2 - Model For Human Operator

Figure 3 - Revised Model For Compensatory Tracking Task

Figure 4 - Diagram of an Information Channel (9:67)

Table 1 - Forcing Function Design

Sinusoid Number	Harmonic	Frequency (rad/sec)	Amplitude (volts)		
			FF1	FF2	FF3
1	3	0.230	0.979	0.867	1.035
2	7	0.537	0.979	0.867	1.032
3	13	0.997	0.979	0.867	1.022
4	19	1.457	0.978	0.867	1.008
5	29	2.224	0.971	0.867	0.973
6	37	2.838	0.959	0.866	0.935
7	53	4.065	0.903	0.863	0.840
8	79	6.059	0.717	0.845	0.650
9	107	8.207	0.495	0.798	0.441
10	139	10.661	0.321	0.704	0.245
11	211	16.184	0.146	0.448	0.038
12	283	21.706	0.082	0.276	0.003
13	419	32.137	0.037	0.131	0.001
14	587	45.022	0.019	0.067	0.001
15	839	64.351	0.009	0.033	0.000

Table 2 - Summary Chart for Forcing Function #1

Subject	Entropy		Capacity		Equivocation	
	Passive	Active	Passive	Active	Passive	Active
1	13.91	12.12	7.40	7.60	6.51	4.52
2	13.10	14.81	9.94	10.15	3.16	3.95
3	12.65	14.87	9.35	10.67	3.30	4.20
4	15.19	14.39	8.93	8.41	6.26	5.98
5	14.33	14.43	9.86	10.85	4.47	3.58
6	16.58	17.48	10.25	8.59	6.33	8.89

Note: All values are in bits/sec.

Table 3 - Summary Chart for Forcing Function #2

Subject	Entropy		Capacity		Equivocation	
	Passive	Active	Passive	Active	Passive	Active
1	12.66	13.91	5.78	7.64	6.88	6.27
2	13.00	16.36	8.21	11.34	4.79	5.02
3	14.03	15.64	9.66	11.32	4.37	4.32
4	12.28	15.17	7.36	7.57	4.89	7.60
5	14.27	15.27	9.20	10.90	5.07	4.37
6	12.79	17.63	7.08	8.23	5.71	9.40

Note: All value in bits/sec.

Table 4 - Summary Chart for Forcing Function #3

Subject	Entropy		Capacity		Equivocation	
	Passive	Active	Passive	Active	Passive	Active
1	11.26	10.88	6.84	7.65	4.42	3.23
2	12.34	13.11	9.75	10.26	2.59	2.85
3	11.22	12.68	9.08	9.69	2.14	2.99
4	15.11	14.18	8.01	8.43	7.10	5.75
5	13.57	12.41	9.47	9.80	4.10	2.61
6	12.66	16.65	8.72	9.29	3.94	7.36

Note: All values in bits/second.